

Five Safes Workshop: Facilitators Guide

Introduction

This Five Safes framework course, Intro to the Five Safes, provides participants with an introduction to the Five Safes Framework. This workshop will also demonstrate that by having an understanding of the framework, it will allow researchers who use and produce data, especially sensitive data to do it in a safe manner.

This course is an output of the CADRE (Coordinated, Access for Data and Environments) project. The project, has more than 10 external partners, including ARDC who are the main co-investor. The main project office is based at the Australian Data Archive (ADA), ANU. The project is building a platform, by using the Five Safes framework as a way to operationalise the application and approval for access to sensitive dataset(s).

Target Audience

The target audience is HDR students and early career researchers. This audience is more motivated and open to learning new concepts. It is important to build their knowledge when it comes to undertaking safe research practices, especially when it comes to working with sensitive data.

Given time constraints on senior academics, it is envisioned that their ability to attend a session like this would be limited. It is hoped that participants can see the value in the training and advocate for peers, colleagues and supervisors to complete the supplementary online Five Safes module.

The target audience for this course consists of individuals responsible for:

- Requesting access to secondary sensitive or restricted data.
- Producing their own sensitive data.
- Research data management.

Prior to taking this course, these individuals should be able to:

- Understand the data collection or accessing secondary data process.

Prior to taking this course, these individuals should know:

- Basic research data management terminology

Time

Under 3 hours, divided into two sessions:

- Session 1: One and a half hour to establish the foundations of the Five Safes
- Break: 15 mins
- Session 2: One hour to discuss the two additional Safes as well as consolidate learning with activities, follow up questions.

Suggested Materials and Supplies

Participants: pens, notebook, laptop, printed copies of the activities

Facilitator: laptop or USB

Technology: Internet access, projector and screen, external speakers

Technology Considerations

The workshop has been designed so that participants would only require their mobile phones for online polling but as most participants bring laptops, they would assume they can access the internet. Bringing a laptop over a notebook and pen is not encouraged because of the temptation to answer emails or do other tasks which distract the learner from the workshop.

Structure for the Workshop

1. Introduction, Welcome to Country and any housekeeping.
Give a brief introduction about yourself.
Welcome to Country or Acknowledgement of Country. If you are facilitating a workshop in a new location, ensure you find out the correct Country and pronunciation, for that location.
2. Online polling.
Set up 2-3 polls for the audience to engage and participate in. See below for some past examples. Your institution should have access to polling software but if not, a free one is: <https://www.mentimeter.com/features/live-polling>
ANU gives access to: [Poll Everywhere](#)

You can also create a QR code as an alternative way for learners to access the poll.

Which best describes you?

HDR student	A
Academic	B
Professional	C
Other	D

3. Introduce each of the five safes. Use examples that is relevant to your audience. Some slides within the PPT file can be adapted or you might find rearranging the sequence makes more sense to you and your style of presenting.
4. Two additional safes.
5. Individual and group activities.
6. Questions.
7. Reflection.
8. Next steps.

Table 2. How confidentiality in ABS microdata is maintained by the Five Safes

	Basic microdata	Detailed microdata
Safe Settings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users must store data in their own secure environment. • Users must limit access to approved users within their organisation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access is via the ABS DataLab, which has a two-factor authentication for user login. • All user access and actions are logged and may be audited. • No data can be removed from the ABS DataLab and external data cannot be brought into the ABS DataLab without being checked and approved by the ABS.
Safe Projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data must be used for statistical or research purposes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projects are assessed by the ABS, with the assessment considering the statistical purpose, public value and type of analysis.
Safe People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The head of the user’s organisation must sign legally binding undertaking and agree to conditions of use. • Breaches of protocols or disclosure of information may be subject to legal sanctions and/or legal proceedings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users must be authorised by the ABS, sign legally binding undertaking, declaration of compliance, and agree to conditions of use. • Users must undertake training related to data confidentiality and roles and responsibilities. • Breaches of protocols or disclosure of information may be subject to sanctions and/or legal proceedings.
Safe Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Users must comply with certain rules for outputs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A clearance process is applied to the final output before it can be taken outside the ABS DataLab. • Outputs may be compared for consistency with the original project proposal.
Safe Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is survey data or Census sample. • Direct identifiers are removed. • Data is available at broad levels only (e.g. state, ‘capital city’/‘balance of state’). • Variables are aggregated (e.g. 5 year age groupings). • Units with high disclosure risk may be treated by having their values rounded, perturbed, top/bottom-coded, suppressed, or swapped with another unit, or the unit may be removed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data is mostly survey data or Census sample, but complex integrated administrative data is also available. • Direct identifiers are removed. • For more sensitive data, only the variables needed for a project are provided to a user. • Units with high disclosure risk may be treated by having their values rounded, perturbed, top/bottom-coded, suppressed, swapped with another unit, or the unit may be removed.

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About This Guide

The facilitator guide is a companion to the PowerPoint file, for the *Intro to the Five Safes workshop* but includes more detail on instruction and specific information about presentation of the material and facilitation of exercises. It has been developed to assist facilitators who have little to no existing knowledge of the Five Safes framework.

Course Schedule

This course schedule is to give you guidance, based on an in-person delivery model. However, the course could be adapted for online or even for a pre-recorded format (so it could be used for self-paced learning). For recorded delivery some of the below would need to be adapted, for example the pre-reading and case study activities.

Recommended Delivery Schedule	
Schedule	Activity
Registration – confirmation email	Provide any pre-reading or resources to watch, that need to be completed beforehand
Day of the workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome to Country • Housekeeping • Online poll • History of the Five Safes • Brief overview of what are the Five Safes • Go through each of the Safes • Guide the group through activities • Further learning: online module

Course Administration

Pre-Course Activities

1. **Determine who will be the best audience for this training.**
Recommendation: HDR students and/or early career researchers who might have more of a willingness to attend. Originally this training was developed for the HASS disciplines but it can be for anyone who collect or want to access sensitive data.
2. **Schedule the training.**
Recommendation: Plan the workshop for a date when availability for attendees and rooms will be better. This might be in an induction week (HDR students) or semester/teaching break. If you don't have access to a permanent space for training, book early (and this might also influence when you hold the workshop).
3. **Set up registration and any pre-requisites.**
Recommendation: Determine how you will track who will attend the training. This might be through internal event registration processes or external, such as Eventbrite or Humanitix. You will need to decide if the participants will need to bring anything for the training (laptop for example) and if you want to set them any pre-course activities they have to complete. It is recommended you select at least one of the below for participants to do beforehand:
 - [Five Safes Video](#)- UK Data Service 4min
 - [Five Safes Video](#) – CADRE 3:11min
 - [Five Safes](#) – Brief Overview
 - [Five Safes: designing data access for research](#) – paper, 27 pages
 - [The 'Five Safes': a framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions](#) – paper, 5 pages

Also consider including some questions in your registration form to capture information such as department/school/faculty affiliation, interest areas for research and job role. This will help personalise the session (point #6).

4. Promote the training.

Recommendation: Utilise internal communication channels to promote the training. This could include: college/faculty/school (email) newsletters; HDR students (email) newsletters; course conveners and social media. Also consider writing personal emails to staff members who can distribute the event information to cohorts of people they know, especially those who supervise HDR students.

5. Create a short questionnaire for post-workshop feedback.

Recommendation: This questionnaire should allow your participants to provide feedback that can help improve the content and delivery of the training. It should take less than a few minutes to complete. Questionnaires can easily be put together using [Microsoft forms](#) or [Qualtrics](#) (if your organisation has an account).

6. Adapt any content or activities for the audience.

Recommendation: Once you have a good idea of who will attend, review the content and activities to see if any changes need to be made. Learners will retain knowledge if it is content that they can apply within their area of interest.

Software and Equipment

Minimal software and equipment is required. This is based on holding the workshop in a room that provides access to internet, ability to display the PowerPoint on a screen and Wi-Fi. Check beforehand if a laptop can be plugged in or there is an option in the room to access the slides through a desktop or laptop. Have the slides saved in a cloud storage location but also a copy on USB as back-up.

Course Evaluation

It is good practice to give learners the opportunity to provide feedback after the workshop. This allows the facilitator to continuously evaluate any parts that can be improved.

A short survey can be put together within Microsoft forms or Qualtrics.

- [ANU access to Qualtrics](#)
- [Microsoft Information for surveys](#)
- [External users of Qualtrics](#)

Make sure the survey is short and default is anonymous. However, give the option to provide their email address for further follow-up if they consent.

Updates to the Course Material

While a good deal of effort has gone into the development of this training course, it is inevitable that both facilitators and participants will find errors, omissions or other shortcomings that need to be addressed. Please encourage the participants to bring to your attention any problems they experience with the course. You, the facilitator, should communicate any problems that are identified to the CADRE project team on: admin@cadre5safes.org.au. Then corrections can be made in subsequent versions of the course materials.

About Facilitating

Given the time allocated to this training is short, it is important to find a balance between facilitating the learning as a lecture style format and providing opportunity for learners to complete activities to reinforce the content.

1. Make sure you understand the content you will present.
2. Refer to the facilitator guide and read the notes. If the schedule allows, try to add information that supports or highlights the points being made in the slide (e.g., add examples from your own experience or that are relevant to the audience).
3. Assess if all slides are required or you need to add in more. Each facilitator has their own style of presenting and this can impact the length of the presentation. Make sure enough time is left to include at least one activity.
4. Don't be afraid to admit what you don't know. There may be a lot of questions for which you don't immediately know the answer. You can always put the question out to the audience, especially if it is a domain specific question that a participant might be willing to share their own experience. Often, when learners hear from other participants that validates a point you are trying to convey, it can help to
5. Encourage participation. This might be allowing questions throughout the presentation or setting group-based activities.
6. At the end if there is time, ask participants to share the challenges they face when it comes to sensitive data.

Sample Pre-Event e-Mail to Participants

BCC: <<Participants' e-mail Addresses>>
Subject: Intro to the Five Safes Workshop <<or change to the title your institution has named the workshop>>

Hi Everyone

I'm looking forward to having you attend the Intro to the Five Safes workshop that begins <<day, dd/mm/yy>>. My name is <<your name>> and I'll be your facilitator. Currently, I am working as a <<position>> at <<department/centre/organisation>> I look forward to facilitating this course and learning from you.

As this course is short, it is important you allocate some time to complete the pre-reading and watch the video. This should not take more than <<XXmins>>.

Reading & Video:

<<see course administration for list of below>>
<<insert link to at least one reading>>
<<insert link to at least one video>>

Again, I look forward to seeing you all <<next/this>> week.

Thanks

Course Facilitator Notes

A script as such has not been provided. This is because each facilitator will have their own style of presenting the necessary information.

Reminders:

Footer – update to the correct department and the date of the workshop

Slide #	Topic	Notes
3	CADRE	<p>CADRE (Coordinated Access for Data, Research and Environments) is a project whose project management office is based at The Australian National University. The project was/is a co-investment from NCRIS via the Australian Research Data Commons, ANU and other partners in higher education as well as government.</p>
7	History	<p>The framework was conceived early in the 2000's in the UK. Around the mid 2000's the term Five Safes was applied. The intention of the framework was to help decision making about the use of sensitive data. This is done by applying statistical disclosure control measure in place.</p> <p>Further reading:</p> <p>Original Five Safes website</p> <p>UK Data Service on Five Safes</p>
8	Five Safes	<p>This video is an easy to understand introduction.</p> <p>https://youtu.be/VeHDtSGEaJQ</p>
9	<p>Question: Why is it important that research data is shared with other researchers?</p>	<p>A question to ask the group. Hopefully they come up with some similar answers to what is on the next slide.</p>

10	Context	<p>By attending this workshop, attendees will have a better overview of how they can apply the Five Safes when sharing their own primary data and also understand the decisions for data custodians when they want to access someone else's data.</p> <p>It is important to note that each of the Safes are not considered in isolation when using to make decisions. Depending on the data, one or more Safes might be weighted more in comparison to others. The Five Safes framework needs to be considered in context.</p>
11	Safe People	<p>Are the researcher's identity and their history in relation to research (working with data) verifiable? This could be as simple as them having a valid email attached to a research institution. All information shared by the data applicant (researcher) adds up to painting a picture that this person has the skills and experience to work with sensitive data safely. From a data custodian or owner, this information is captured and presented in the application for access (one example).</p>
12-15	Safe Project	<p>The data applicant (researcher) needs to demonstrate that the data requested is appropriate for their project. By providing details about what the project is and how the data will answer the research question, gives credibility to the application. The person or people assessing the data application don't need to know every single detail but often applicants don't put in enough detail. It is important to provide enough to meet the above requirements (right data for right project).</p>
16-17	Safe Data	<p>Safe data tries to apply the necessary but minimum protections to the data. If data is de-identified too much it could be deemed useless. Protections can be put in place so that data can remain useful.</p>

18	Safe Setting	Where the data be accessed and analysed? Does this provide enough protection/security so that anyone not authorised can't access the data?
19	Safe Output	The data owner/custodian makes decisions so that the data applicant has clear guidelines on what their expectations are for a safe output. By using t
21	Safe Organisation Safe Group	The CADRE project (ARDC is a co-investor) looked at including 2 x additional safes. The partners believed that safe people did not cover organisations or groups explicitly. They believed it was important to explore how organisations and groups play a part in risk assessments. You can read more on the project's conceptual framework here , pages 32-33.
22	Data Availability and Transparency Act 2022	<p>The Act was passed in April 2022. It was a key recommendation from the Productivity Commission Inquiry Report into Data Availability and Use (2017).</p> <p>The objectives of the Act are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • serve the public interest by promoting better availability of public sector data • enable the sharing of public sector data consistently with the Privacy Act 1988 and use of appropriate security safeguards • enhance integrity and transparency in sharing public sector data • build confidence in the use of public sector data, and • establish institutional arrangements for sharing public sector data. <p>Not all government agencies have to share their data because of the sensitive nature as well as national security risks.</p> <p>The process for universities in particular to become accredited data service providers has been time consuming and resource intensive.</p>

23	Group Activity: ABS	This is an example from the Australian Bureau of Statistics and how they apply the Five Safes. Go through each example row by row and ask learners to volunteer to provide answers. There is a copy of this diagram in the facilitator notes that you can print off to provide a copy per table or per person.
24	Group Activity: Hypothetical	<p>This activity is to reinforce what the content previously introduced. It is also a good opportunity for learners to engage in discussion as there can be a variety of answers. It will also lead onto the introduction of the CADRE platform.</p> <p>Examples of possible answers: 1. Research on bipolar. Safe = Safe project. 2. Data analysis; mental health researcher experience etc. Safe= Safe people. 3. A safe cloud environment such as FileSender (AARNET)</p>
25	CADRE Platform	<p>CADRE – Coordinated Access for Data, Research and Environments. It is a co-investment project with ARDC and several partners – ANU, Swinburne, UNSW, UoM and several government agencies.</p> <p>The project aims to operationalise the Five Safes for the application and approval to access sensitive datasets for HASS researchers. The project aims to use existing sources of information to construct a profile of a researcher so they can be assessed as ‘safe’ and the information they provide about their project or research questions also demonstrates that it is the correct data for their research. It also looks to provide this overview to the person or people who will provide approvals to access the sensitive data. It is hoped this will decrease the time researchers wait for approvals.</p>

Websites

DAT Act 2022: <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2022A00011>
<https://www.datacommissioner.gov.au/law/dat-act>

CADRE Conceptual Framework v1.0 <https://zenodo.org/record/5748611>

ABS for group activity: <https://www.abs.gov.au/about/data-services/data-confidentiality-guide/five-safes-framework#examples-from-the-abs>

CADRE Five Safes online module: <https://learning.cadre5safes.org.au/>

Case study and Group Activities for print out.

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Second case study

Hypothetical case study.

You are the owner of a dataset. You are contemplating making it available to request by data applicants in the Australian Data Archive (ADA). This data consists of qualitative and quantitative. You wanted to determine if there was an intersection between age, race and gender when it came to a positive diagnosis of bipolar and what the impact was on their current and/or future relationships. You undertook interviews with 50 people who self-identified with bipolar. In your consent form you stated that their answers would be kept on file and the participants name would be excluded but location of the interview would not. You also advised that their data will be shared with other researchers who are undertaking similar research. It will be accessed by application only.

In your group consider the below questions. Come up with a solution(s) and which Safe they relate to. You have been allocated the role of data custodian at the ADA and can make these decisions on behalf of the original researcher.

1. What type of research would you give a green light to access?
2. What skills and experience should the data applicant have?
3. How would a data applicant access the data once approved?
4. Will you allow applications to be made by personal email addresses?